

Genetic Algorithms and Their Effectiveness in NP-Complete Problems: Sudoku

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Abstract—Genetic Algorithms are heuristic algorithms generally used in non-deterministic problems and is popular as it is usable in a variety of situations, to which it may fare, either extremely well or the opposite. This paper aims to introduce genetic algorithms in the context of sudokus as well as provide an example to showcase how effective it is at reaching the optimal solution and to compare how well it does to other, more focused methods.

Index Terms—Genetic Algorithm, Evolutionary Computing, Sudoku, Data Science

I. INTRODUCTION

Sudoku is a game that first appeared in 1979 [1] in a puzzle magazine and has since, been a very popular pastime for many. This puzzle has also become subject of numerous studies and a testing ground for many different approaches in algorithmic design within computer science.

The puzzle itself, is quite simple – usually a 9×9 grid containing smaller 3×3 grids within, with random cells having a number placed in them. The goal of the puzzle is to successfully place a number in every cell, in such a way that every row, column and grid have no duplicates and contains every number from one to nine. However simple the rules appear to be - reliably finding the optimal solution proves to be difficult, especially as the grid becomes a $n \times n$ grid, exponentially increasing in both space and time.

5	3			7				
6			1	9	5			
	9	8					6	
8				6				3
4			8		3			1
7				2				6
	6					2	8	
			4	1	9			5
				8			7	9

Figure 1. A typical 9×9 sudoku

As such, this is a good starting point for getting started with genetic algorithms practically as well as

to demonstrate why sudokus pose as a difficult obstacle in the general effectiveness of the algorithm.

II. GENERAL STRUCTURE OF A GENETIC ALGORITHM

A basic genetic algorithm consists of smaller components that all run in a cycle [8], looping over until either the limit of cycles has been reached or an optimal solution was found. The components are such:

A. Fitness Evaluation

- To evaluate how fit each individual i.e to evaluate how close said individual is to the optimal solution.
- The way fitness can be calculated depends on the problem state and parameters.

B. Ranking

- Sorting out the individuals based on their fitness scores.

C. Selection

- Selecting a percentage of the population for the next step – crossover.
- There are a number of selection methods, each suited for different situations and with their own pros and cons.

D. Crossover

- Members of the selected population combine with each other to form new, “children”: a combination of the two member’s data.
- The type of crossover depends on the how the data is structured and the limitations set by the problem.

E. Mutation.

- This is something that can happen at any stage of the cycle, where a individual is randomly “mutated” – to have it’s data be randomly edited.

However, before all of these components, a starting population must be created in order to rank and select to start the algorithm.

III. GENETIC ALGORITHMS IN CONTEXT WITH SUDOKU

For the purpose of simplicity, a 4×4 sudoku, or “shidoku”, will be used.

A. Starting population

Creating a starting population is as easy as just placing random numbers within the grids. However, to speed up the process and reducing the search space; I, instead, will opt to create random combinations with no duplicates in every row. This decision has a major impact on the time taken to find the optimal solution [11] as seen in Fig. 2. Especially in the later difficulties.

We can provide mathematical backing to this by permutating the possible combinations for both outcomes. Not optimizing the search space would mean the created possible solutions can have duplicates of any number in either rows or columns. Taking the difficulty to be, for example, 0.75, the possible combinations reach to 4^{12} . Setting a constraint to no duplicates in rows, this number reduces to just 6^4 (given 1 pre-filled cell in each row), which is around 70,000 times less than before adding this additional constraint. Due to the nature of genetic algorithms, populations tend to stay within a distance genetically to the initial population, hence why initial search space reduction is important.

Figure 2. Average time (seconds) taken to solve 500 sudoku of each difficulty

The difficulties are presented in terms of the numbers of cells that are empty. To illustrate this, a difficulty of 0.75 would have a 4×4 sudoku of 12 empty cells

B. Selection Process

Determining fitness values differ between the target problem set and the data being used. Within this paper, I decided to weigh every repeated number in a row, column and grid to 1, adding up with each repeated number. Therefore, having a smaller fitness

value would equate to a higher rank. Hence, having a final fitness score of 0 would account to be the problem being solved.

Tournament selection performed the best compared to other selection types, while the fitness proportionate selection performed the poorest, ignoring the random selection. The less performant methods tended to either converge prematurely or took much longer to reach the global optima, as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The best combinations per generation for four different selection methods (lower is better)

The Boltzmann procedure [4] was tuned at a starting temperature of 100, a temperature decay of 0.95 and a final temperature of 0.1.

C. Specialised Crossover

There are many types of crossovers, and may be suitable depending on the type of data being propagated. One method would be to utilize the *OX crossover* [2] across every row and/or column, however this tended to be computationally expensive with little to no gain in change per points per generation. An alternative, was to randomly choose between a crossover based on either the grid (Figure 4), column and row. This produced much better results as it was more diverse without sacrificing the quality of better combinations, and was overall less expensive.

Figure 4. Crossover by grid

D. Mutation

One of the main frustrations in a genetic algorithm is the eventual lack of population diversity. Without diversity, the algorithm will prematurely converge and land on a local optima. To prevent this, one of the strategies used is to mutate the existing population after crossover occurs.

To preserve the identity of the overall combination, *shuffling* the movable cells was done. Given a row, R_0 , with movable cells, j , and duplicate cells, k . There are $\frac{j!}{k!}$ possible mutated R_0 . Because of this, diversity tends to be less of a worry, if mutated at the right rate. When the mutation rate is too low, there is a chance for the population to undergo *genetic drift* [10], which will cause the diversity to take a hit and in turn, lead to premature convergence. With a mutation too high, the better solutions will have a lower chance to pass on and evolve in future populations.

However, the algorithm can be improved by introducing elitism, which guarantees the best combinations will survive to the next cycle. [11]

IV. GENETIC ALGORITHMS AND NP-COMPLETE PROBLEMS

A problem is said to be defined as NP-Complete if it is in NP, and is NP-Hard – which can be established from Karp-reductions [9, pg99]. Sudoku is classified as NP-Complete. Takayuki [3] has proven that a nxn sudoku can be reduced to a partial latin square. Which can further be reduced to a 4-SAT problem, which has been proven to be a np-complete problem. This classification is also due to the fact that the verification of a sudoku can be done in polynomial time, $O(n^2)$ but finding the solution can *only* be done in non-polynomial time.

However, as demonstrated earlier and from other papers, [5] and [6], it is trivial to conclude that while GA are a novel approach, it is not necessarily the best one, at least in the case of Sudokus. To showcase this, Table 1 contains data regarding various algorithms to solve sudokus.

Difficulty	Avg Time for Backtracking/s	Avg time for Brute Forcing/s	Avg time for Genetic Algorithms/s
0.3	0.00661	0.00393	0.00105
0.4	0.00350	0.00348	0.00089
0.5	0.00377	0.00455	0.23061
0.6	0.00397	0.00577	0.52693
0.7	0.00768	0.00493	1.69145
0.8	0.00532	0.00627	2.88694
0.9	0.00429	0.00395	3.18341

Table 1. For 500 iterations, the average time taken to solve each sudoku puzzle with the respective difficulty. Bold identifies the fastest time.

V. FINAL CONCLUSIONS

Table 1 showcased how Genetic Algorithms within the context of this problem set tends to perform much poorly compared to more specific algorithms and even just naïve brute forcing methods. The surprising effectiveness of the brute forcing method may be attributed to the low number of possible combinations of a 4x4 sudoku.

Genetic algorithms prove to be less than suited in the domain of Sudoku and even number classification problems. However, it's potential to solve more complex problem sets with much more rigorous constraints is unmatched to traditional methods [7]. Attributing to its adaptability to virtually any constraint allows it to be a potential solution to most, if not all, situations.

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